

ABOUT THE STRATEGY OF FINANCING

The student of TSUE Corporate governance

faculty: Saloev Xumoyun

The teacher of TSUE foreign languages

department: Khikmatov Dilshodjon

Abstract. The given pie charts provide details how expenditure by local authorities of Someland fluctuated over the years of 1980, 1990 and 2000. As expected, the lion's share of the budget was allocated to higher education in all three reporting periods.

Keywords: banking system, Big Four Banks, Industrial and commercial bank, Construction bank

To begin with 1980, The most finance demanded sectors were Higher education and K-12 Education, their portion was 35% and 25% of the total government expenses accordingly. The tendency continued over the next decades with small changes. To be precise, 45% and 20% in 1990 and 40% and 18% in 2000 respectively. On the other hand, government investment on Transport and Health/human resources went through an erratic period, both sections outriped each in every decade. As for Environmental services, the financial stream towards them increased slightly over the period while the government decreased expenses steadily on the rest of the sectors. The rose numbers were from 4% to 9% and the declined ones were 6% to 1% correspondingly.

One can infer that the Someland government made different decisions about the strategy of financing the improvement of the nation's infrastructure each decade.

The given graphs depict how the UK people's spending behavior developed between the time period of 1971 and 2001. In brief, the residents started paying more for cars by the end, before most of the money had been spent on food.

To be detailed, in the beginning, the food sector took 44% of an individual's income, twice as expensive as cars. By 2001, British people changed their habits dramatically in some aspects. For example, they doubled payment on cars (43%) and restaurants (14%), whereas they started economizing money on food (14%) and books (1%). Three and six times less than previous ones accordingly. Interestingly, expense on petrol went down, by 2% even though expenditure on cars doubled. In addition, 2001 was remembered by entering a new section, computers into locals' spending habits. Their portion in the expenses accounted for 12%.

The reason for the decrease in money paid for food probably can be explained by the fact that people started eating out. And one more analysis on impacting different sectors on each other could be that the new sector, computers, apparently caused the decline of spending income towards books that computers allow users to download and share free ebooks.

The People's Republic of China was established in 1st October 1949 year. But China has a great centuries-old history beginning from 221BC. First similar to bank organizations was created in 10th century during the "Sun" dynasty. Those organizations were able to accept deposits, giving credit loans, exchange currency and transactions between cities, but there were limited people to use such services. In our days Chinese Banking system is one of the most various in world financial market. According to report¹ of the end of 2020 year, total amount of China banking assets rich 49 trillion dollars, which is 2.5 times more than USA banking assets and 3 times more than GDP of China. Most crucial leap of banking system developing was in middle of 19th century, for the period of entering European trade companies. British Oriental Bank was the first bank opened branch in China in 1840 year. Then other banks, participations of Treaty of Nanjing², also started entering in China

¹ https://eng.spdb.com.cn/investor_relations/annual_report/202106/P020210601536091873402.pdf

²

https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%9D%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%BA%D0%B8%D0%BD%D1%81%D0%BA%D0%B8%D0%B9_%D0%B4%D0%BE%D0%B3%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%BE%D1%80

financial market. At the end of 19th century, there were 9 foreign banks (Deutsch-Asiatische Bank, Yokohama Specie Bank, Banque de l'Indochine, Russo-Asiatic Bank, British Oriental Bank, The Hongkong and Shanghai Banking Corporation and etc.) with 45 branch, those banks were emitting money, accept deposits and giving credit loans. Interesting fact is that time China did not have even one own bank in its own financial market until 1897, when The Imperial Bank of China was established, but main shareholders and management was also foreign investors. After 8 years was found the Central Bank of China named Cinq State Bank. After overthrowing Cinq dynasty at 1911 Bank was renamed to Bank of China. In 1928 year was found new Central Bank of China. People's Bank of China, which was organized during Chinese revolution in 1949, in 1950 was most powerful bank with monopolistic position by displacing and absorbing other banks until 1970. When Deng Xiaoping became a leader of country, banking system was fully reorganized. People's Bank of China's activities were divided between 4 state banks: Industrial and commercial bank, construction bank, agricultural bank and bank of China, while People's Bank of China fully stopped commercial activity and performs only Central Bank obligations. Modern Banking system of China consist of 3 levels and controlling by All China Regulatory Commission.

First level consist of 4 banks: People's China Bank, State Development Bank, Agricultural Development Bank, Export-import Bank. As it was mentioned earlier People's China Bank in our days performs duties of Central Bank. Other 3 banks are responsible for developing in industry sphere, agricultural sphere and external trading.

List of used sources:

1. Xasanova, S. (2021). Rus tilshunosligida frazeologizmlarning tadqiqi: rus tilshunosligida frazeologizmlarning tadqiqi. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(7).
2. Shaxzoda, X. (2020). Lexical Properties Of Pu Songling Novels. *The American journal of social science and education innovations*.

3. Xasanova, S. (2022). XITOIY VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA FE'L FRAZEOLOGIZMLARINING ANTONOMIYA HODISASI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(Special Issue 29), 188-197.

4. Khasanova, S. A. Q. (2022). Analysis of verb phraseological units in chinese. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 11(5), 280-283.